

ORGANIZATION OF DENTAL CARE IN THE PRIVATE HEALTHCARE SECTOR

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Abstract: Dental health plays an important role in the overall well-being of society. In recent decades, the role of the private sector in the healthcare system has increased significantly, including in the field of dental services. The evolution of organizational models of dental care requires detailed analysis in order to identify optimal approaches to providing high-quality and affordable care to the population. Organizing effective dental care is a key aspect of ensuring the health and quality of life of the population. This article discusses strategies for improving the accessibility and quality of dental care for the population.

Key words: dentistry, private sector, organization of care, quality of dental services, accessibility of medical care.

Number of private dental clinics: As of 2023, there are about 1,200 private dental clinics and offices in Uzbekistan. Most of them are concentrated in large cities, such as Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Namangan. About 5,500 dentists and 7,800 dental technicians and nurses work in private dental clinics in Uzbekistan. The average number of staff in one private clinic is 10-15 people. Private dental clinics in Uzbekistan provide more than 3.2 million dental services annually. The most popular services are caries treatment, prosthetics, implantation, whitening and cosmetic dentistry.

Turning to private dental clinics offers a number of advantages compared to public institutions, including:

-Quality of service: Private clinics often offer a high level of service, ranging from short waiting times for appointments to an individual approach to each patient. Service is usually more attentive and personalized.

-Innovative equipment and technologies: Private clinics have the opportunity to invest in modern equipment and the latest technologies faster than government institutions. This provides access to the best diagnostic and treatment methods.

-Wide range of services: Private dental clinics often offer a wider range of services, including cosmetic dentistry, orthodontics and dental implantation, along with traditional procedures.

- Flexible opening hours: Opening hours of private clinics are usually more convenient and flexible, including evenings and weekends, which is especially important for working and busy people.

-Price transparency: In private clinics, pricing policies are often more transparent, and patients know the cost of treatment in advance without hidden fees or additional costs.

-Highly qualified personnel: Private clinics attract qualified specialists who provide services at a high level, thanks to competitive pay and working conditions.

-Individualized approach to treatment: In private clinics, patients can expect more carefully tailored treatment plans that take into account their specific needs and preferences.

-Comfort and Atmosphere: Private clinics often invest in creating a comfortable and attractive environment for patients to ensure that visiting the dentist is as pleasant and painless an experience as possible. These benefits make private dental clinics the preferred choice for many patients, as they provide high-quality treatment in a comfortable environment, although this may come with a higher cost.

The organization of dental care for the population includes the following aspects: needs analysis: assess the current state of dental care in the region, identify the main problems and needs of the population, program development: develop a dental care program that includes the availability of services, priority areas of treatment, and

disease prevention measures , infrastructure and equipment: provide the necessary infrastructure and equipment to provide quality dental services, including equipment for diagnosis, treatment and prevention, personnel: ensure the availability of qualified specialists - dentists, nurses, administrative staff, etc., financing: develop financing mechanisms dental care programs, including government subsidies, insurance, paid services and other sources of funding, prevention and education: carry out activities to prevent dental diseases and increase public awareness of proper oral care, monitoring and evaluation: systematically monitor the quality and availability of dental care , evaluate the effectiveness of the program and make adjustments if necessary.

In modern society, dental health plays a key role in the overall well-being of the population. However, despite significant achievements in the medical field, many regions face problems with the availability and quality of dental care. This requires a systematic assessment of the current state of dental care to identify the major problems and needs of the population. The first step in assessing the state of dental care in a region is to analyze available data and statistics. This includes assessing the number of dental institutions, the availability of qualified specialists, the availability of services for various population groups, etc. To obtain a more complete picture, it is necessary to conduct a survey among the population of the region. The survey should cover questions about the availability of dental care, level of satisfaction with the quality of services, problems faced by patients in receiving treatment, and their needs. Studying statistics on the incidence of dental diseases allows us to identify the main problem areas. It is also important to study risk factors for the development of dental diseases, such as nutrition, oral hygiene, the level of knowledge of the population about proper dental care, etc. An important aspect of assessing the current state of dental care is assessing the availability of services for various population groups. This includes geographic accessibility, affordability, availability of specialized services and other aspects. Based on the analysis, we can identify the main problems and needs of the population in the field of dental care. This

information is the basis for developing a dental care improvement program aimed at increasing access and quality of services and reducing the incidence of dental diseases.

The main aspects of organizing dental care in the private healthcare sector: Licensing and accreditation: obtaining a license for medical activities in the field of dentistry in accordance with the requirements of regulatory authorities, passing accreditation of a private dental clinic to confirm compliance with established quality standards. Obtaining a license to practice medicine in the field of dentistry is a mandatory requirement for private dental clinics. A license is issued by an authorized government agency after checking the clinic's compliance with established licensing requirements and conditions. Requirements include the availability of the necessary equipment, compliance with sanitary and epidemiological standards, personnel qualifications, etc. The process of obtaining a license can take up to several months, so it is necessary to begin preparing documents in a timely manner. Accreditation of a private dental clinic is a voluntary procedure confirming the clinic's compliance with established quality standards. The main goals of accreditation are to improve the quality of medical services, patient safety and improve management processes. Accreditation is carried out by accrediting organizations and involves a comprehensive assessment of the clinic's activities. Successful completion of accreditation increases patient confidence and the competitiveness of a private clinic. Licensing and accreditation are therefore key elements for the legitimate operation and quality assurance of private dental practice.

Equipment and infrastructure: Equipping a dental office or clinic with modern, safe and effective medical devices. Creating comfortable conditions for patients, including comfortable rooms, waiting areas, and reception areas.

Staffing: Selection of highly qualified dentists, dentists and paramedical personnel. Ensuring continuous professional development of employees.

Formation of pricing policy: Establishing competitive prices for dental services, taking into account market trends and the income level of the target audience.

Providing flexible financial plans and loyalty programs for patients.

Marketing and Promotion: Developing an effective marketing strategy to attract new patients. Using modern communication channels such as website, social networks, advertising.

Quality Management: Implementation of a quality management system to ensure a high level of service. Regular monitoring of patient satisfaction and process improvement.

Conclusion. The growth of the private sector in dentistry is helping to improve the availability and quality of dental care. However, this process is fraught with a number of challenges, such as the need to regulate the quality of services, pricing and ensure equal access for all segments of the population. Effective organization of dental care requires an integrated approach that combines the efforts of the state, medical institutions, educational institutions and public organizations. By introducing modern technologies, preventive programs and improving the qualifications of medical personnel, it is possible to improve the accessibility and quality of dental care for all segments of the population. The key to success is an integrated approach that takes into account all aspects of organizing a private dental practice. At the same time, it is important to ensure that the services provided comply with high medical standards and ethical standards.

Literature:

1. Dustova G. K., Kurbanov A. A., Kurbonov K. R. Measures taken to prevent coronavirus infection in Samarkand region //Экономика и социум. – 2020. – №. 11. – С. 102-105.
2. Teshaboeva K., Israilova S., Qurbonov A. PREVENTION MEASURES FOR MAJOR NON-EPIDEMIC DISEASES //МОЛОДОЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬ: ВЫЗОВЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ. – 2021. – С. 97-99.

3. Dustova G. K., Kurbanov A. A. SAMARQAND VILOYATI AHOLISI ORASIDA COVID-19 KASALLIGIDAN KEYINGI BEMORLARGA KUZATILGAN KASALLIKNING ASORATI VA KASALLIKLARNING O'ZIGA XOS KECHISH XUSUSIYATLARI //Eurasian Journal of Medical and Natural Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 186-189.
4. Mamasoliyeva Shokhista Abdugapparovna, & Kurbanov Anvar Alamovich. (2023). Mechanisms for Increasing the Economic and Organizational Efficiency of the Management of the Medical Service Sector. Texas Journal of Medical Science, 18, 150–153.
5. A'lamovich K. A., Rabbimovich N. A. MARKAZIY ASAB TIZIMI VA KASALLIKLARI //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 25. – №. 2. – С. 14-18.
6. A'lamovich K. A., Rabbimovich N. A. KAMQONLIK KASALLIGINING KELIB CHIQISHI, PROFILAKTIKASI VA DAVOLASH USULLARI //TADQIQOTLAR. – 2024. – Т. 30. – №. 3. – С. 140-143.
7. Курбанов Анвар Аъламович. (2024). ИННОВАЦИИ В СИСТЕМЕ ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ: ПУТЬ К УСТОЙЧИВОМУ РАЗВИТИЮ. Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования, 14(1), 226–228
8. Sharofitdinovna N. P., Abduroziqovich K. A., Dilovarovna B. J. EMERGENCY CARE ORGANIZATION //Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 18-20.
9. Sharofitdinovna N. P., Alamovich K. A., Dilovarovna B. J. ANALYSIS OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG STUDENTS //Web of Medicine: Journal of Medicine, Practice and Nursing. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 30-33.
10. Юлдашева Ш. А., Нуритдинова П. Ш. ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА ЗДОРОВЬЕ ЧЕЛОВЕКА //World of Scientific news in Science. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 131-136.

11. Nuritdinova , P. S., & Kushmatova , D. E. (2022). The role of nursing staff in the formation of a healthy lifestyle of children. Евразийский журнал медицинских и естественных наук, 2(5), 122–128.
12. Parvina Sharofitdinovna Nuritdinova. (2023). FEATURES OF FORMING A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE IN STUDENTS. World Bulletin of Public Health,21,191-193.Retrievedfrom <https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbph/article/view/2598>
13. Parvina N.Sh. Promotion of a healthy lifestyle among the population // Экономика и социум. – 2022. – No 1(92). – P. 151-157.
14. Sharofitdinovna N. P., Shomurotovna R. Y. FARINGIT KASALLIGI HAMDA UNING OLDINI OLISH //Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования. – 2023. – Т. 5. – №. 1. – С. 169-174.
15. Нуритдинова П. Ш., Юлдашева Ш. А. ОСНОВЫ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ КАК КЛЮЧ К ЗДОРОВЬЮ //World of Scientific news in Science. – 2024. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 315-320.